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Integrating Artificial Intelligence for Effective and Efficient Management of Secondary Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution

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ABSTRACT

Epistemological breakthroughs and conscious advancements of mankind are the preoccupation and focus of any meaningful educational provision. One breakthrough in the 21st century that has multifaceted application and whose utility has become epical assets to humanity is artificial intelligence. As a multifaceted educational breakthrough, education especially in the area of management can be said to be the most beneficiary of this 21st century multidimensional innovation. Using the philosophical research methodology and theoretically guided by social constructivism and human capital theory, this study discusses the potentials of artificial intelligence in the effective management and administration of secondary education in the fourth industrial revolution which prioritizes digitalization. The study among other things establishes and demonstrates that artificial intelligence is instrumental in promoting administrative and management efficiency and productivity of teachers and learners in secondary education. The study makes recommendations, part of which is that the acquisition of knowledge of artificial intelligence should be made a topmost priority among learners and that government should make investments in artificial intelligence a priority for national development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Secondary education, Management, Fourth industrial revolution.

INTRODUCTION

One fact that is as sure as day and night is that man has an inherent desire to aspire for growth and development, to develop visions that are capable of enabling him master and conquer his environment, to consciously have dreams that can trigger ambitions for the expansion of his territories and above all the development of attitudinal dispositions and inclinations to exploit and explore the resource of his environment for his survival. These drives are the trajectories that influence and determine the line of choice, action, success and failure of man across cultures.

In alignment with nature, these multiple directions that are central to man's choices, actions, success and failure coexist in ways that make competition for attention inevitable. Interestingly, all the competing options in the existential quest for man's survival are achievable on two conditions namely the prevalence of order and man's ability to systematically arrange and address his existential quests in order of their importance. A route for translating the conditions above into reality in man's existential quests for survival is education.

Education and its provision is foundational and fundamental for the wellbeing of the individual and the collective survival of the institutions in the state. Investments in the citizens of state through education are the vectors and routes for the visible development of the state and this symbiotic relationship between investments in the citizens and the development of the state makes investment in education a litmus test for determining how responsible and/or accountable the leaders are to the people and their state.

Investment in a people through education brings about the reformation and transformation of the people into critical and creative assets, a development that translates into empowering the citizens into resisting marginalization, enslavement and deprivation in the hands of fellow individuals and the state. As instrument and institution for turning a people into assets, education enables a people to make meaningful contributions for the development of their state as well as strives to promote order, discipline, innovations and institutional behaviours that are supportive of democracy and good governance. In fact, moral, social, economic, political, scientific and technological innovations for radicalizing and revolutionizing a people and their state easily become norms through education.

Education is the hub that drives innovation in all spheres of human endeavours and the 21st century is synonymous with ground breaking breakthroughs and innovations in all areas of life of man. One innovation in the 21st century that has brought about epical, radical, phenomenal and revolutionary transformations in addition to being a great asset with potentials to increasing efficiency, productivity as well as maximum human happiness (Nwaokugha & Abiakwu, 2024) in all areas of human endeavours is artificial intelligence. The epistemological breakthroughs that evolved or that gave rise to artificial intelligence has expanded and widened visions, increased efficiency and productivity, boosted critical thinking and creativity so much that there is what Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:182) call promotion of “unhindered and unlimited access to areas and environment which prior to this time had remained unimaginable, unthinkable and impossible”. Developments in artificial intelligence have simplified the provision of services especially in the area of human capital development. In its rampaging onslaught for improving the quality of human existence, artificial intelligence has been a great asset in the education industry generally and in the area of management of secondary education in particular. These benefit of artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education show and illuminate positive lights that promise to make waves especially in this era of fourth industrial revolution with its epical focus no digitalization, computerization, collaboration and networking.

As obvious as this can be, a worrisome trend and a cause for concern is that not many persons are aware of the foundational and fundamental potentials of artificial intelligence and fourth industrial revolution in the efficient and effective management of secondary education. It is correct that a collaboration of the two can prioritize a paradigm shift on how institutions can function better in the society. This study therefore is focused on creating awareness and insights on what humanity stands to gain by integrating artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education particularly in the fourth industrial revolution. The study is timely as the society needs to be guided through the provision of adjustment strategies and response mechanisms to innovations that in addition to occurring in split seconds have become the defining indexes of the 21st century. In fact, knowledge of management skills and capabilities which this study is sure to generate can be sure guarantee and sure bet for effective utilization and effective exploration of opportunities and challenges that artificial intelligence can pop up in the secondary education level of education.

The theoretical frameworks that guide the study are human capital theory and social constructivism. Human capital theory as a theory of knowledge construction posits that investments in human beings through education, training and acquisition of skills are orchestrated and conscious drives for the development of a state as the individuals who are so far invested in are potential carriers of the genes and vectors through which the curiosity, dream and aspirations of a state to develop can be translated into reality. This is strongly anchored on the premise that development does not trigger itself but can be triggered and stimulated by human beings who carry the genes that can robustly translate into development. What is inherently implied here is that citizens who have been invested in through education can be predisposed to initiating behavioural actions that can be supportive and conducive of development. In fact, the ability to possess the genes upon which development springs up is only possible when investments have been made in human being or citizens of the state that are desirous of development. In a way, the focus and thesis of human capital theory is that providing education for the citizens of a state is an investment that has multiple potentials namely the development of the citizens of

state into assets and using such assets to increase the acquisition of skills, knowledge and entrepreneurial expertise that are sure bets for increasing productivity and operational effectiveness and efficiency and the combinations of skills, knowledge, entrepreneurial expertise can naturally leads to the development of a people and their state.

On the other hand social constructivism according to Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:252) invokes a meaning that revolves around the thesis that:

Human beings are the principal actors and agents that produce, generate meaning, build and construct knowledge, development that suggests that no knowledge is ready made or manufactured anywhere, rather that knowledge grows and develops out of human consciousness through interactions, dialogues, manipulations and communication that systematically and logically derive from day to day experiences of persons with other institutions in the society.

From the epistemological lens of social constructivism, knowledge construction or knowledge development is a shared property among members of the society who share the same vision, the same curiosity, the same interest and who are desirous of expanding, refuting and extending the frontiers of knowledge. Central and inherent to the evolution of knowledge from the perspectives of social constructivism is the willingness and determination of the individual or individuals who so wish to develop knowledge or break through the frontiers of knowledge to collaborate with one another, interact with one another, discuss issues or topics that border on knowledge that is of common interest with one another and above all demonstrate attitudes that are phenomenally and robustly receptive to critical and creative thinking. What is at the centre of the above is the recognition of an observation put forward by Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:180) that “human beings are the architects, builders, and constructors of whatever meaning that exists in the world of knowledge” and this observation is in complete agreement or alignment with the position already reached by Liu and Matthew (2005:387), who in unambiguous terms write that “knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment”.

The suitability of human capital theory and social constructivism for this study lies in the fact that states or societies that are desirous of institutional and national developments must make quality investments in their citizens a topmost priority so as to raise an army of skilled workforce who can initiate and manage innovations upon which the institutional and national development of the state depends. The strength of the above can further be rekindled by the inherent recognition that knowledge of whatever configuration upon which the development of the people and their state resides lies with man, courtesy of his ability to be critical, creative and aided by man’s ability to cooperate, collaborate, interact and share experiences with other members of the society.

Methodologically, this study employs the qualitative or the philosophical research methods, which is noted for its numerous features, principal of which is its heavy reliance on what Angadi (2019:37) call “the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research”, where the researcher functions as the primary instrument for the collection and analysis of data and priority is given to meaning and semantic clarity through robust attention to rigours of thought. Other features that are associated with the qualitative or philosophical research method is highlighted by Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10), when they write that:

Qualitative research is often exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numeral data such as interviews,

generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

Qualitative or philosophical research methodology is justified for this study on the ground that every branch of knowledge benefits from philosophical reflections and this particular study is no exception (Nwoke & Nwaokugha, 2024:59). In fact, this methodology is beneficial to scholars and researchers in many ways namely, it boosts researchers' and scholars' confidence through empowering and emboldening them into investigating and researching topics which ordinarily may seem unthinkable and un-contemplatable, widens scholars' and researchers' investigative skills, promotes collaboration as well as helps to extend and expand epistemological frontiers, whose overall analysis results in the development of the individual and the national development of his state.

A common tradition about studies that adopt the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is to give in-depth and detailed focus on concepts that are key in the study and to this we now turn.

Artificial Intelligence

The 21st century is synonymous with phenomenal and epical epistemological breakthroughs that have reshaped the global community through transformative and revolutionary innovations that have potentially left impressions in virtually all areas of human endeavours. Epistemological innovations in the 21st century have set and hit the ground rolling in revolutionary trends that have opened up spaces and created opportunities so much that people and institutions now have unlimited and unhindered access to geographical locations and environment which over the years can be considered real only in man-made tales. Having unlimited and unhindered access to geographical locations and environments can be a pointer that man and his institutions may have received a super boost for his economy as that can translate into exploiting and exploring more environment for resources that can boost the economy of the individual and that of the state. It can be said with all amount of assurance and certainty that space exploration has brought about transformative breakthroughs in the communication industry and similar exploration of water bodies have expanded and extended the epistemological space, widened space for recreation and more importantly boosted critical and creative thinking. One epistemological breakthrough that affords man and his institutions the opportunities to explore the universe for man's advantage is Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Artificial intelligence is the centre of attraction and a destination of choice in the 21st century in as much as epistemological breakthroughs are concern. Becoming relevant and identifying with the trending rhythms of the time in the knowledge industry is the extent in which the activities of individuals and institutions are AI complaint or align and comply with the prescriptions of artificial intelligence. True, there is no area of human endeavour where the use of artificial intelligence has not been established or where the seal of artificial intelligence has not been noted; and this comprehensive spread and inclusiveness, though a blessing has major challenge namely the inability of stakeholders to agree on a one size fit all definition of artificial intelligence. This is the point raised by Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:183) when they write that "artificial intelligence is a 21st century technological innovation which scholars describe in different ways", implying that artificial intelligence can be associated with a plethora and avalanche of definitions, where each definer or scholar providing such definition may say it from the angle or discipline where he is operating from. In all of these, there can be features that may be present in all such endeavours and attempts at defining artificial intelligence and some researchers and scholars have chosen not to border themselves with definition of artificial intelligence but to prioritize its features and usefulness in the day to day affairs of man in the 21st century. This study will attempt to define artificial intelligence as well as highlight its potentials in the survival of man in the 21st century.

Artificial intelligence according to Baker and Smith (2019) does not refer to a simple technology but is defined as "computers (that) perform cognitive tasks usually associated with human mind particularly learning and solving problem". In the views of Lydia, Vidhyavathi and Malathi (2023:75), artificial

intelligence is an automated systems that can engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction and using data for complex processing task while Aggarwal (2018) writes that artificial intelligence is a general term that refers to diverse analytic methods and these methods can be classified as machine learning, neural networks and deep learning. According to Shi and Zheng (2006), artificial intelligence is a research subfield belonging to computer science whose nodal concern is the stimulation, extension and enhancement of human intelligence while Akinwalere and Iranov (2022) write that artificial intelligence is a technological innovation that is committed to making the lives of human a lot earlier.

Any insightful and analytic scrutiny of the foregoing can locate and situate artificial intelligence as a technological innovation where computers and machines are structured and programmed to function and perform tasks that human beings do. That computers and technology are basic or fundamental for artificial intelligence to exist point in the direction that artificial intelligence is deep rooted in multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and cross disciplinary paradigms and all these are aided by critical and creative thinking. One discipline that is instrumental for the progress and success in the evolution of artificial intelligence is education and one discipline that has epically and phenomenally benefited from artificial intelligence is education, ranging from teaching and learning to management and administration of educational institutions particularly at the secondary education level.

Secondary Education

There are developments across the globe that states share in common irrespective of their developmental sophistication or lack of it; every state across the globe holds education in high esteem and makes it a fundamental human rights of every citizen. That education is the fundamental human rights of every citizen makes its provision a topmost social service that any responsible leader and every responsible state provides for their citizens. There are many reasons why states hold education in high esteem to the point of making it a human right. The litmus or index for determining the level of development of any state is the quality of education and quality of civil-mindedness of the citizens of the state. How educated citizens of a state are helps to make governance easier as well as serves as index or yardstick for determining the amount of respect a state enjoys in comity of states. In fact, states that make education a topmost priority maximally benefit from such investment as citizens so far invested in turn out to be great assets and are foundations for the development of the state. This simply means that it is in the best interests of states to provide education for their citizens and this symbiotic relationship between education and the development of the state makes education a subject matter upon which politics is played.

It is true and remains so that the education industry is at the heart and centre of the politics of states and this has given rise to individual states packaging and structuring their education in ways that the individual states deem it fit. A common feature with the education systems of states is their receptivity to fragmentations and policy summersaults. The fragmentation of education in some states follows trajectories where there is primary education levels, secondary education levels and tertiary education levels. Management and official attention from the states is usually focused at levels of education as they exist in states. This study is focused on the secondary education level in Nigeria.

Secondary education according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:18) is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary level. What this means in Nigeria is that secondary education is at the middle of the education pyramid or structure and is specially designed to ensure that its products internalize and imbibe virtues that can promote in them the ability to live as useful members of the society as well as develop capacity that can enable them pursue higher education. It is on this basis that the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:18) writes that secondary education shall:

- (a) Provide all primary school learners with the opportunity for education of a high level irrespective of sex, social, status, religious and ethnic background
- (b) Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles

- (c) Provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce of sub-professional grades
- (d) Develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world cultural heritage
- (e) Inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence
- (f) Foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity
- (g) Raise generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens
- (h) Provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.

The above is revealing and part of what it reveals is that the secondary education level in Nigeria is crucial and critical for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian state and base on this observation, the possibility is there that the number of learners at this level of education can be very high. The implication is that this level of education requires and calls for extra manpower, extra-investment, extra funding and extra management skills and processes. Anyone who has a good knowledge of the history of education in Nigeria can attest to the fact that, education generally and second education in particular is in a deplorable condition. These revelations point in the direction that integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into the management of secondary education can be a receptive option for restoring hope and confidence in the management of secondary education in Nigeria.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution

Human consciousness and awareness have made it possible and clearer that events and happenings as they occur in the affairs of man can be better undertaken, understood and follow up actions and analyses can be better reflected upon when such events and happenings are systematically and sequentially presented with special recognition and notice of critical features that mark them out in the order of their occurrence. Events and happenings occur virtually in all areas of human endeavours and how far they resonate in influencing history depend on the area of their occurrence and the magnitude of their importance in changing the narratives about institutions and the survival of man. Notable developments have occurred in the area of production of goods and services across the world and in fact, the production of goods and services has gone through notable phases of change, shift and transition and experts and specialists in production circles capture such transitions, shifts or changes in production dynamics as industrial revolution.

What has been said above can be slightly restated that what has come to be known as industrial revolution or the concept of industrial revolution is a chronicling of the phases that man and his institutions have passed through the history of production of goods and services. Production of goods and services was first and foremost undertaken through manual labour but has gone through many phases which each of the industrial revolutions stands for. The process of production of goods and services has transitioned from manual labour to automated mechanical work, from workshop set up to production systems in the factories and to what can be called automated computerized systems. At the centre of production especially starting from the middle of the 20th century, industrial revolution transitioned to the use of robots and artificial intelligences in the production of goods and services. This is where credit can be given to Ali, Ayad and Al Rubaie (2022:197), who write that:

The Industrial Revolution is the process of rapid change witnessed by the countries of Europe through their adoption of scientific research projects, which led them to move from the era of agriculture and handicrafts to the generation of an industry that depends on mechanization.

It therefore follows that the idea of industrial revolution is a transition, a shift or a change from the process of manual production of goods and services to a sophisticated machine, computer, digital and information technology dominated or driven way of production of goods and services that principally involves the use of machines, robots and artificial intelligence. The above is an idea of industrial revolution in the present dispensation which was not so in the first industrial revolution that prioritize or focused on the use of machine that solely depended on steam power, water and the railway. The second industrial revolution exclusively focused on electricity and its capacity to expand the production of goods and services via telephone, radio and television. The third industrial revolution focused on automation and is consequently called digital revolution where emphasis is on the integration of computers, electronics, internet and information and communication technology.

The fourth industrial revolution started at the end of the 20th century in the United States and china (Ali *et al* 2022: 198) and can be said to be unique and what accounts for its uniqueness is its ability and capacity to be a combination of all areas of focus of other industrial revolutions before it, in addition to exponentially, phenomenally and epically, expanding the innovative space across all epistemological frontiers so massive and comprehensive that Ali *et al* (2022) call it the integration of the “physical, digital and the biological world” with epical and exponential potentials to leave indelible impressions on all areas of human endeavours with unmatched and unprecedented “speed, depth and breadth”. The massive and comprehensive influence of the fourth industrial revolution has been phenomenal in term of innovative technological breakthroughs as it is associated with nanotechnology, artificial intelligence, internet of mobile phone, bitcoin and blockchain, smart clothes and implantable technologies (Ali *et al*, 2022) , no wonder Schewab (2016) refers to it as “a set of new technologies”. In all of these, one thing is sure: the ground breaking breakthroughs of the fourth industrial revolution is symbolic for the education industry as technological innovations as well as a robust platform for wider publicity of such innovations and innovative breakthroughs. Such massive innovative developments via the fourth industrial revolution can be effectively harnessed and used across many domains of education including management secondary education.

Possible ways of Integrating Artificial Intelligence in the Management of Secondary Education in Nigeria

The broad aim of secondary education in Nigeria implicates that tier or level of education as one where the possibility of participation by learners in Nigeria can be very high and the level of education is one that seriously needs adequate planning, supervision, organization, coordination, monitoring and control before there can be effective and meaningful results. These responsibilities require an army of committed and dedicated teachers or workforce who in addition to being committed and dedicated must be adequate in number. Be this as it may, anyone who is conversant with the history of education in Nigeria generally and issues of commitment and dedication by teacher to duties at the secondary education level can admit without any form of critical and reflective thinking that secondary education in Nigeria lacks teachers in adequate number and the plight of learners at this level of education is compounded and made more complex by the fact the available teachers are not committed and are not dedicated. This lacuna and missing gap makes case for the integration of artificial intelligence into the management of secondary education in Nigeria. Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:183) call attention on how artificial intelligence can help in the management of secondary education when they write that “in most developing states where the states have lackadaisical attitudes towards education and fundamentally demonstrate this through non-recruitment of teachers in commensurate numbers, effective use of artificial intelligence can come to the rescue of the citizens”. The management of secondary education can leverage on the fact that effective use of artificial intelligence can provide instruction to the teeming number of learners at this level of education. What this means is that effective use of artificial intelligence has the capacity to lower the cost of providing education to its barest minimum.

Integrating artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education in Nigeria can assist principals in ascertaining the originality or otherwise of credentials, and assignments submitted for assessments to the management by teachers and students. The awareness that artificial intelligence can dictate false claims has the force to instill on teacher and learners a consciousness to stick to moral rules by way of not indulging in questionable deals. Management of any secondary education institution can be said to be on the trajectory for genuine national development if morality is instilled in learners and artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education can do this.

Effective integration of artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education in Nigeria can be extended in providing periodic assessment of teachers' instructional and pedagogical efficiency, capability and effectiveness in the discharge of their duties. What is implicated here is that artificial intelligence has the ability to monitor and keep records of the individual performance of teachers in the course of their teaching learners in the classroom and this record can guide managers in secondary education on the performance of every teacher in the school. In fact, this type of objective assessment can aim secondary education managers with lines of actions to take in the near future as it concerns identifying teachers to be sacked or possible management decisions to take so as to strengthen or reinvent professional practices that can enhance efficiency and productivity.

It can be said and said very strongly that artificial intelligence brings a lot of relief to the managers of secondary education especially during examinations as artificial intelligence automates examinations through making marking and scoring very easy. This mean receiving scores after examinations can no longer be a burden to secondary education managers.

Integrating artificial intelligence in the management of secondary education can be a springboard for the introduction of 21st century innovations in the management of schools. One innovation that can become norm in a regime of artificial intelligence in secondary education is individualized instruction. This orientation in secondary education can be a sure bet in enhancing equity and equality of educational opportunity, and attainment of social justice in the affairs of a state. What is said here is that individualizing and personalizing instruction through the use of artificial intelligence can enhance access to education by a greater number of learners.

CONCLUSION

The 21st century is synonymous with innovations and these innovations are products of critical and creative thinking where the education industry is the point of their origin as well as a direct beneficiary of the entire innovation process. Most of the 21st century innovations have triggered revolutionary reforms and transformations so much that there are epical and phenomenal improvements in the quality of life of man and his institutions. Innovations that have brought so much transformations in the education industry are artificial intelligence and fourth industrial revolution. By their nature, artificial intelligence and the fourth industrial revolution are multidisciplinary inter-disciplinary and cross-disciplinary enterprise where technology, computers, digitalization, networking, information and telecommunications, machines etc play active roles. The multifaceted functions of artificial intelligence and focus on fourth industrial revolution on digitalization and networking are receptive to all areas of education. In this paper, attention has specifically been focused on the use of artificial intelligence and fourth industrial revolution in the management of secondary education in Nigeria. There are strong indications that so much needs to be done if we are to maximally benefit from our quests to make innovations norms in the management of education. Innovations are capital intensive, the government should make adequate budgetary provisions for innovations in secondary education institution. As innovation are dependent on technology the government should ensure that there is adequate supply of power. There should also be adequate supply of qualified personnel. Managers of secondary education institutions should ensure that knowledge of artificial intelligence becomes a topmost priority among learners and government should invest heavily in artificial intelligence infrastructure in secondary education in Nigeria.

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